

Title: Membracinae

PAUL STAPLETON, SARC, Queen's University Belfast

MICHAEL SPEERS, SARC, Queen's University Belfast

1. PROGRAM NOTES

This improvised performance deploys metastable networks of vibrotactile and audible feedback to intertwine Stapleton's custom-made electroacoustic instrument Volatile Assemblage (aka VOLA) with Speers's acoustic drums driven by air pumps and transducers. The music that emerges through such intra-actions tends towards unforeseen behaviours and contingent structures, akin to the steering of a small ship on tempestuous waters, or the communication of insects through the rapid bouncing of abdomens against a shared substrate, thereby creating a kind of 'aesthetic interfacing' between performers, instruments, audience, environment and their collective movements through time and space.

Fig. 1. Nodes of Membracinae.

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2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

This project builds on (and questions) our established instrument design and improvised music performance practices. It is an improvisational social aesthetic [1] that motivates our efforts to intertwine our instruments in a manner that embraces ambiguity and unpredictability [2], which are preconditions for the types of precarious musical-social relationships that we are interested in exploring in our artistic research. This performance proposal is also informed by *feedback musicianship* [3 and 4], an area that has seen increased attention in the NIME community in recent years [5, 6, 7], with a genealogy that arguably includes practitioners as diverse as Jimi Hendrix, David Tudor and Viola Yip, as well as the systems theories of Wiener, Ashby, Pask, Varela, Maturana, Rosch, Di Paulo and De Jaegher (to name a few).

Specifically, we are interested in how networks of feedback can reconfigure our relationships to our instruments, with an emphasis on distributing control beyond the agency of one individual actor (human, or otherwise), and the responsibility to *pay close attention* to what such a scenario produces. In the process, we aim to make explicit that our instruments and our own selves are not static objects, devices or even isolated subjectivities, but rather co-constituted and evolving processes [8, 9] produced together through our dynamic intra-actions [10]. Conceptually, our approach also resonates with the work of Tim Shaw and John Bowers [11], from where we adopt the notion of ‘aesthetic interfacing’ as a collaborative process between performers, instruments, audience, environment and their collective movements through time and space.

Our title *Membracinae* pays homage to a subfamily of treehoppers. These insects communicate through the rapid bouncing of abdomens against a shared substrate, a relationship that is more than metaphorical in our own practice of vibro-tactile and sonic communication through mobile electroacoustic transducers placed against the material surfaces of our instruments (see figure 2 below). These dynamic multisensory entanglements take place and emerge from two different nodes, as seen in both figures 1 & 2, and described as follows:

Node A: Upcycled materials (scrap metal, an old repurposed hard drive, hacked electronic circuits, used turntables and abused vinyl records) are placed in combination with relatively low-cost embedded computers (Arduino, LattePanda Alpha), transducers, amplifiers, contact microphones, rechargeable batteries, beaters, pics, slides, strings, a bow, ping-pong balls, cappuccino whisks and other found objects. A notable component of this node is a simple amplitude modulation programme running on an Arduino coupled to a VCA, which decreases the amplitude of feedback signals based on increases in amplitude of

the same signal but only during positive phases of the waveform cycle, thus sometimes producing a tremolo effect that changes rate based on the frequency and which in turn regulates the maximum amplitude of feedback in this part of the node. The Arduino acts as a voltage controller for the analogue VCA, which allows the signal that passes to the transducers across both nodes to avoid being digitised.

Node B: Electric air pumps feed tubes, which are coupled with drum heads using small, inverted cymbals and brass mouthpieces. When activated this creates vibration of the drum head against the metallic coupler - producing a loud, rich drone - a kind of unstable acoustic oscillator. Various sizes of drum shell, head material and objects placed on the drum orient the system towards a wide range of states. Tiny shifts in the tension of the drum head, position of the coupler, air pressure and interference from surface transducers or loudspeakers interact with this system to create rich, complex sound built from layers of beating tones, rattling and noise - recalling the behaviour of a microphone feedback system.

As this will be an improvised performance with a somewhat unpredictable system, we would ideally like some flexibility with the performance length, with an ideal target of between 15-20 minutes.

Fig. 2. Rehearsal Setup for Membracinae. See video link below.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

Our setup is largely self-contained. All instruments will be provided by us. However, we will need a table and access to mains power. Our first choice would be to perform at one of the ‘local Utrecht stages’ (i.e. club venues), but our setup is adaptable to a wide variety of venues. For larger venues we would require sound reinforcement through a PA. For smaller venues, we are happy to play at the level of our acoustic instruments and transducers but would require one small amplifier (e.g. keyboard, guitar or bass practice amp). We are happy to discuss lighting and staging once the venue is confirmed. We would ideally need at least one hour of setup and rehearsal time in the venue.

4. MEDIA LINK(S)

- Rehearsal Video: <https://vimeo.com/912578933/04846dacc>

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ETHICAL STANDARDS

We have no conflicts of interest in carrying out this work (financial nor non-financial). Our work does not have any implications that would require a research ethics review (e.g. the research does not involve the participation of animal subjects, human or otherwise).

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